

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM AND ITS RESEARCH IN THE WORLD AND IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article explores the historical peculiarities of the emergence and development of gastronomic tourism in the modern world. The authors pay attention to the various approaches to the classification of gastronomic tourism by domestic scholars. Particular attention is paid to the features of the emergence of gastronomic tourism in Ukraine as a new direction of tourist activity.

Keywords: tourism, tourist activity, gastronomic tourism, gastronomic festival.

Introduction. Gastronomic tourism as a separate type of tourist activity belongs to the category of new types of tourism. However, it is fair to note that its origins originated in ancient times. The first gastronomic tourists can be called the first travelers who began to actively conquer new lands and cultures in the era of the Great Geographical Discoveries (Marco Polo, Afanasy Nikitin). It was these travelers who left the first written records of new lands, culture and the way of life of local residents. They did not ignore the gastronomic features of these peoples. A certain contribution to the acquaintance of Europeans with exotic products and spices was made by medieval merchants who brought unusual products to Europe, such as exotic fruits, spices, nuts, wines and oils. Impressions of these products became the basis for impressions of the country as a whole, its people and customs. However, much later, this direction of travel became an independent science and branch of tourism.

Interpretation of the summation of research materials. The year of the emergence of the term "gastronomic tourism" and the emergence of the gastronomic tourism direction as a separate type of tourist activity is considered to be 1998. It was then that the concept of "gastronomic tourism" was first introduced into circulation by the American researcher L. Long to denote the knowledge of the culture of other peoples through the culture of food consumption and acquaintance with local cuisine.

Since then, scientific research on the gastronomic direction of tourism has begun. Already in 2001, the world saw the first scientific article, and later - a monograph on the topic of gastronomic tourism by researcher Eric Wolf. Two years later, in 2003, the International Association of Gastronomic Tourism was established in the USA (since 2012 - the World Association of Gastronomic Tourism). The main task that this organization set for itself was to instill the culture of food and beverage consumption, as well as to help private enterprises develop on the basis of interest in the development of gastronomic culture. It was thanks to this association that for the first time the concept of "culinary tourism", which was then commonly used, was replaced by "gastronomic tourism". Today, the association has representative offices in 139 countries of the world, and the number of its members is about 100 thousand people [1].

Since 2015, the World Association of Gastronomic Tourism has been organizing an annual conference, the theme of which is related to solving the problems of the development of gastronomic tourism in the modern world. A wide range of specialists in this field of tourism, as well as managers of travel companies, representatives of the hotel and restaurant business, etc., take part in this conference.

In the following years, research institutes and research organizations on the problems of gastronomic tourism were founded in different countries of the

world. In particular, in 2006, the International Institute of Culinary Tourism was established in the USA under the World Association of Gastronomic Tourism. At the same time, travel companies are emerging that specialize in providing gastronomic tourism services in the USA ("Gourmet on Tour"), Great Britain ("The International kitchen") and Italy ("Gourmet Getaways"). These companies were the first on the tourism market to represent this direction, but very soon gastronomic tours became popular in different countries of Europe and the world, which led to the emergence of a significant number of new tourist enterprises and organizations in this tourism industry.

In the future, the rapid development of gastronomic tourism and its rapid growth in popularity led to the creation of the International Union of Gastronomic Cities Delice. Today, this organization includes more than 20 countries of the world that promote the gastronomic culture of tourism. They annually organize numerous festivals, exhibitions, fairs and gastronomic locations that allow tourists to get acquainted with the local cuisine, learn about the identity of the population of this region and country through the prism of cultural gastronomic identity.

Ukraine was not aloof from world tourism trends, and in 2013 the Association for the Promotion of Wine and Gastronomic Tourism was organized in our country. This organization unites on a voluntary basis institutions, organizations, enterprises that work in the field of gastronomic tourism, as well as educational institutions that train specialists in the field of restaurant business, food and wine industries, etc.

The association aims to actively promote the development of Ukrainian gastronomic and wine tourism, the development and presentation of Ukrainian enogastronomic products on the national and international tourist market, as well as the promotion and support of domestic producers of related products.

The Association for the Promotion of Wine and Gastronomic Tourism sets itself a number of important tasks aimed at promoting the comprehensive development of gastronomic tourism in Ukraine. Among them are: organizing excursions, tours, conferences, and festivals in Ukraine focusing on gastronomic tourism; conducting marketing research on Ukrainian regions regarding the development of wine and gastronomic tourism; establishing international cooperation in the field; combining the efforts of all organizations working in the fields of tourism, hotel and restaurant business, wine, and food industry to promote gastronomic tourism in Ukraine, etc.

In the scientific works of domestic and foreign tourism researchers, classifications of gastronomic tourism are presented, which have certain differences. For example, S. Gataulina, V. Shykerinets, and H. Vyshnevskaya divide gastronomic tourism into rural and urban, depending on the locality of travel.

S. Salamatina classifies gastronomic tourism into the following directions: chocolate, wine, agro-, cheese, tea, honey, coffee, fruit-berry, fish, and mixed.

Each of these types aims to acquaint tourists with the features and technology of preparing certain dishes and to conduct tastings. Most Ukrainian researchers use this classification, and Y. Obukhov asserts that these types can be called gastronomic monotourism. According to this scholar's definition, gastronomic monotourism is a type of tourism dedicated to familiarizing oneself with a single culinary product.

There is a separate classification of gastronomic tourism according to travel directions: festive and festival tourism.

Researchers also highlight a new type of tourism - gastronomic diplomacy, which is classified as a special type of tourist activity. This type of gastronomic tourism has a clearly defined target audience - diplomats, politicians, representatives of countries at the international level. It involves knowledge of the peculiarities of national cuisine, combining business etiquette with historical-cultural values of countries through the culture of consuming food and beverages.

All the above classifications of gastronomic tourism can be combined according to classification features - by the purpose of travel, by the location of travel, by the direction of travel, by the type of gastronomic product, etc.

Conclusions. So, gastronomic tourism turned out to be quite new. Its first definition was formulated by E. Wolf at the beginning of the 21st century. Subsequently, the gastronomic direction as a phenomenon and tourist direction began to develop rapidly in almost all countries of the world. Today, there are several classifications of gastrotourism, which can be combined according to the direction of travel, location, type of gastronomic product, etc.

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